

Participatory tools

SCENARIO DESIGN + BACK-CASTING EXERCISE – BACK FROM THE FUTURE TOGETHER

INNOVATE TOGETHER DURING THE PROJECT PERIOD: CO-CREATION FOR INNOVATION

How to build innovation together?

Take advantage of the diversity of actors (skills, points of view, context, etc.) to innovate. Participatory methods help to organize time for creation and collective production. The aim is to allow everyone to contribute something and to exchange freely.

How to solve it

As for lots of challenges in multi-actor co-creation, it takes time. Your role is to allow time to reflect and adopt/adapt the right participatory methods.

The main words are trust and adaptation to participants. It helps to have a space where everyone can express themselves freely and which encourage exchanges. It would help if you adapted to each person's comfort level with participatory methods

There are different steps:

Brainstorming, exchanges, pooling/agreement, production.

For each stage, the intention is different, which will influence the choice and use of tools.

Plan to capitalize and make sure that you have validated the decisions/steps/advances collectively as you go along so that you do not have to go back to them (unless necessary).

Word of advice

You need to adapt to the partners and their experience in such processes. For some, too much creativity can be scary at first.

One example of a tool to facilitate this stage

Scenario design + back-casting exercise – Back from the future together

Description of the tool

- **What:** To design desired futures (alternatively, neutral futures or also undesirable futures can also be considered) and identify pathways collectively to achieve/to get closed to these futures, engage people in a collective work, create trust

LIAISON Interactive guide to facilitating participatory projects

- **How long:** depending on the objective, 1-2h per step
- **How many:** Minimum 5-4, maximum 20
- **What you'll need:** flip chart, sticky notes, markers

Steps:

Step 1: Build future scenarios together

- The facilitator explains the context and the theme and gives the operational question (something like “Let’s try to design a possible future together in which...”). Setting a consistent, valid, and agreed landscape and timeframe is important.
- The participants identify the elements they would like to see in this future on sticky notes. The facilitator helps to refocus the discussion if it is too broad or, on the contrary, too narrowly focused on one detail.
- The facilitator and participants collect the sticky notes and synthesise and design one scenario to which a title is given. It is also possible that more than one scenario emerges when the harvested elements refer to different, or even conflicting, directions. The title initiates the discussion and reflects the content of the scenario(s).
- The facilitator takes the time to clean up the description of each scenario as a basis for the second step.

Step 2: Reflect on how to get there: starting from the future scenario(s) and moving backward to the present

- Participants identify the actions needed before arriving at the identified scenario future and the opportunities and challenges to be faced. They also identify

the resources needed. If more than one scenario has been identified and deemed worthy of analysis, the different pathways will be explored individually.

- This operation can be repeated 1-2 times (or more, according to time, ambition etc.) to get back to the present through various steps. The facilitator is in charge of organising the proposals throughout the time. Ideally, the last question is, “what can we do tomorrow?”
- In the end, the participants may develop a somewhat chaotic pathway. The facilitator takes time to organise and validate a final version.

Testimony of the use

Stefano Grando, researcher, UNIPI, Italy

Those tools can be used with different aims:

- Build scenarios together,
- Define a detailed action plan,
- Create links around a topic.

It was used to identify pathways to develop sustainable urban food production in Rome. Fifteen local actors (farmers and experts) were gathered for two one-day meetings separated by a fortnight. The facilitator helps avoid mixing up the stages and going into detail too quickly. It also allows for stages of organization of ideas and synthesis that facilitate progress. Depending on the time available and the objective, you can co-construct the scenarios or start from existing proposals taken, for example, from previous exercises or reports.

This tool has different advantages:

- Encourages active stakeholder involvement

LIAISON Interactive guide to facilitating participatory projects

- Allows for a break from the day-to-day work, triggering a wide-horizon reflection
- Stimulates creativity but with a framework to structure
- Encourages to think outside the box

However, you need to keep in mind some points:

- Difficult to discuss a broad issue; clarifying the context is important to avoid chaotic talks
- If the question is too technical, participants tend to focus on 1 or 2 elements. It is interesting but complicated to stop them to discuss the other points.
- Talking about possible remote futures can be complicated with an audience used to concrete, practical issues: adapt to the audience

This method can also be used online. In another example described in a testimony, the method was used to develop sustainable livestock. Twenty researchers from different countries gathered for three online meetings of three hours on three consecutive days.

Doing it online makes some points easier:

- Allowed to work during the covid
- Allowed to bring more people together (no distance constraints)
- Facilitated keeping track of process and outcomes

The disadvantage of online application is that you lose non-verbal communication, which is easier to grasp in face to face meetings. It is more difficult to get shy people to participate, and it is more challenging to adapt to participants' reactions.

Tips:

- Logistic
 - Do not facilitate alone. If you are not doing subgroups, you need at least three facilitators.
 - Provide a glossary, take time to clarify terms for all
 - Plan a visual presentation of the scenarios
- For the facilitator:
 - Start simple
 - Take time. If you only have, for example, 3 hours, choose another method or work with scenarios that have already been established
- Regarding the group:
 - Anticipate the heterogeneity of the group
 - Plan a question wide enough to be able to inspire a scenario reflection, but not too broad (adapt according to the audience)

Another tool: [Snowball technique](#)

